

METHODS OF SELECTING TALENTED CHILDREN FOR HANDBALL SPORT

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on how to select players in the sport of handball and what to pay attention to when selecting.

In the literature, the concept of selection has different definitions: "A systematic process, developed by specialists, to find the most endowed elements for practicing high level sports, also to reveal the most indicated sport players to participate at competitions" "The selection of athletes is understood as the systematic concern of the coaches in order to desist the athletes with the most appropriate skills to practice different sporting disciplines or to designate the best athletes to participate in the competitions provided in the sports timetable". "Selection is an organized and repeated process of early detection of the innate availability of the child, the junior with a complex system of criteria, for his subsequent practicing and specialization in a sport discipline or test." (The game of handball has had an impressive evolution, lately, spectacular even. The level of performance achieved in this stage is very high and it can only be reached by players whose capacity of performance is big enough and

continuously rising. The technique of the game has expanded a lot. New processes emerged that great level handball players execute them with high skill. Also, the tactics of the game, both individual and collective, has improved so that one game situation can have multiple solutions. To reach this kind of level in handball, the training must begin in early childhood. As a result, in the contemporary concept of handball training, the selection of children it's an integrated part of the training system. Specialists have shown that selection must take place as a continuous, rhythmic and active process. The parts of this process are represented into selection and training. The continuous and active character of this activity results from the fact that the selection is carried out twodimensional at all the age stages and value scales of children and juniors the horizontal and the vertical selection. With the exception of the beginner level, where the selection is carried out horizontally at all the other stages, the horizontal selection is

continuously present and the vertical selection is carried out periodically by promotion to the higher level when all the conditions are met.

The selection activity carried out in accordance with the needs of the handball, positively influences the training process. Selection is a repeated action that takes place on several levels on groups of children and young people, with a high degree of complexity, which is carried out over a long period of time. It should not be made under any pressure or near a deadline, to be free of subjectivism. Criteria, rules or selection tests are developed by analyzing the performance of top athletes in a sporting branch, thereby establishing a selection pattern. This model undergoes changes depending on the age of the subjects to which it is reported. As a result, scales for high - performance players are established, continuing with the establishment of the lower level scales - youth, juniors I, juniors II, juniors III, groups of children. In this respect, the selection uses a complex system of criteria and requirements for identifying young talents aspiring to become a successful player. In the "National system for selection and training of children and juniors in there are five types of criteria: medical sport, somatic-physiological, biochemical, psychological and motivational. The medical-sporting criteria act on the selection system by collecting genetic, physiological information from the field of sports medicine to offer the possibility of a directed, performance-oriented selection.

Medical -sport criteria in selection. Specifically, these criteria are the ones that determine the health of the athlete. The state of health is appreciated by a medical examination that includes the anamnesis -

used in the determination of personal and heredocolaterale antecedents; and a thorough medical investigation to show the functionality of the main devices and systems of the human body. This medical examination is recommended to be performed twice a year or as often as necessary to prevent any possible illness. Due to the fact that performance requires daily attendance of athletes in training, health is required to cope with physical and mental stress. This criterion has a great deal of stability in all stages of sports selection, as it is well known that the athlete "must have no condition that contrasts physical exercise." Also, children suffering from cardiovascular disease, congenital or acquired locomotory malformations are not subject to any stage of selection for practicing a dynamic sport. Of particular importance are the cardio-respiratory criteria. Another category of criteria is radiological, which at the level of the selection may indicate certain abnormalities, which may prove incompatible with the practice of some sports.

Somatic-physiological criteria in the selection. The somatic-physiologic criterion is of great importance because the height, the proportions of the body segments, the weight, the body structure and the type of somatic-sexuality lead to the establishment of the optimal constitutional typology according to the practiced sport, having a major importance in the selection. Height is the indicator according to which the development of the coat can be estimated and determined by the anthropometric examination, being a parameter to which the other anthropometric measurements can be reported. The importance of height varies from one sporting branch to another

or from one sample to another, being sports where the height does not influence selection, and in other sports it helps.

The determination of somatic-sexuality also has a great importance in the selection, due to the characteristics of certain sports samples or strands where performance results are associated with a certain masculinity or femininity rate. As well as the medical-sporting criteria, the somatic physiologic criteria are present at all stages of the selection of children and juniors.

Biochemical criteria for selection. The importance of biochemical criteria is given by the biochemical aspects of the body's energy. The biochemical parameter is an important element in the selection and sports training. "Things are explained by the fact that the functioning of the body, in general, and especially in the conditions of effort, is conditioned, first of all, by the energy factor, involved in the formation and restoration of the complex molecules from the simple ones, in the production of thermal energy. The mechanical one, both for internal and external movements, whose osteo-articular and muscular systems are the effector." It is recommended that biochemistry issues be done by a specialist in the field for the accuracy of the results and their interpretation.

Psychological criteria for selection. The model of the high performance athlete also includes a certain profile of personality (will, motor skills, motivation, discipline, conscientiousness, self-sufficiency, etc.), which will allow it to be ranked higher in the sport practiced. Psychological selection and training have grown in recent years, becoming an important factor in sports training and competitions. Due to the fact that in some sports the debut is very early,

and the psycho-behavioral characteristics can't be analyzed objectively, it is necessary to have experienced coaches who observe certain skills shown in childhood, later asserted in adolescence and youth. The action of psychological selection is good to be done in stages of age and after the sports and motive selection has been carried out. The psychological parameters used in sports activity relate to certain aspects of the psychological area: - intelligence - it can be noticed after discussions with the athlete; - qualities of will, ambition, perseverance - seen at a sports training session; - personality structure, temperament, character - these traits can be analyzed both during and outside training; - psychological traction, spatial representation, coordination, reaction rate;

Motive criteria in selection. Traction is the benchmark of the most important selection for most sporting disciplines and disciplines. This is found in all stages of the selection, from the initial to the final one, being evaluated in the form of control samples or rules that are integrated into a system. The content of this system that includes test samples and rules differs from one stage to another in the selection depending on the age and attitude of the athlete. The assessment of the athletes' motorship for each individual and cumulative motor quality is done by analyzing the results recorded in a test set at the base of which is the Standard Fitness Test. In the initial stage of the selection, the emphasis is on the level of development of general motor skills, while in higher stages will be used traction tests characteristic of each sport discipline referring to the technique and tactics of the respective sport. Driving criteria are crucial to establishing the level of physical training.

The control sample bars are those that reflect the individual evolution achieved for each age and level of training. The control samples for handball players are: - 30 m sprint - two attempts, noting the best (preferably the start to take from the 4 meter line and the arrival at the semi-circle of 6 meters opposite) -30 m running in the dribbling, slalom among the piles - the first jar at 6 meters from the starting line, the other 6 piles at 3 meters from each other, the arrival being obligatory with the ball under control (two attempts, noting the best) . The test is for field players only. - 10X30 m continuous run (commuting type) - with the footprint of the markings (start / finish) -Two-leg length jump, landing on two legs - two attempts, noting the best. - Throw away the handball ball at distance with 3 steps - two attempts, noting the best. -Triangle movement (3 complete paths) - the triangle is drawn as follows: the base of the triangle is the straight line of 3 meters of the semicircle of 6 meters, on this base, from the middle rises a perpendicular 3 meters which reaches the semicircle Dotted and what will be the height of the triangle. The sides of the triangle are marked by joining the three points thus obtained. At the top of the three angles and tangent to them is drawn a circle with a diameter of 30 centimeters. It is obligatory to touch the corner of the circle with two attempts, noting the best. e, from the bar (goalkeeper) left up, right top, bottom left, bottom right - the route will repeat 3 times. At the top corners, both bars will be touched, and bottom will touch the last colorful segment on the bottom of the bar - two attempts, noting the best. The formation of groups of beginner children requires a very intense activity from the coaches, done methodically, with patience and with a

sense of professional responsibility. At this level, the selection takes place only horizontally and takes place in three stages: initial selection, preliminary selection and relatively stable selection. The initial selection - this activity begins by delimiting the selection area, continues with watching and selecting the children which is a very important task for the coaches. they will present the beauty of the game, the impressive results that handball has had over the years and the perspective that the children will have if they choose to play this game. Finally this stage ends with the organization of the practical activity. The preliminary selection - this stage marks the beginning between training and selection. This stage consists of practical lessons, during which the coach will observe the children evolution. At the end of it, the coach will operate with the selection criteria, and some of the control tests will be made even 2 or 3 times in a few days. The data from the observation and from the control tests will be used for selecting the children. In this phase, the purpose is to keep the children that prove they are willing to play handball. The relatively stable selection - this stage ends the activity of selecting and forming the groups of children, beginners. The content of this stage is pretty much similar with the stage before. we organize the groups, it continues with lessons of learning and initiation, and periodically new control tests to see the improvement the children made. The data will be compared to the ones for this stage and so there will be chosen 25-30 children with whom it will begin the process of training in handball. The time estimated for this stage is 2-3 months. Conclusions . For the judicious assessment of the results obtained by the children at the parameters included in the somatic and

motor models, the coaches will prove very demanding, in full compliance with the performance requirements at senior age. A rigid interpretation of the results, may lead to mistakes in the selection in the sense that children and juniors who still have enough performance availability can be removed from handball. That is why an elastic but realistic interpretation is needed. It is

obvious that those who do not meet most of the parameters cannot be selected in the upper echelon, not having sufficient resources for handball performance. Those who do not meet the 1 to 2 parameters, but have superior results to other parameters, should not be excluded, but selected as they still have prospects.

References:

1. Demeter A, 1974, Physiological Basics of Physical Education and Schooling, Stadion Publishing House, Bucharest.
2. Dragnea A, Mate-Teodorescu, S, 2002, Sports theory, Fest Press, Bucharest.
3. Drăgan I, 1989, Medical-sport selection and orientation, Sport - Turism Publishing House, Bucharest
4. Epuran M, 1968, Sports psychology, Publishing House of National Council for Physical Education and Sport, Bucharest
5. Ghermănescu IK, Gogăltan V, Jianu E, Negulescu, I, 1983, Handball Theory and Methodology, Didactic and Pedagogical Publishing House, Bucharest
6. Nicu A, 2002, Theory and Methodology of Modern Sports Training, Publishing House of the Romanian Tomorrow Foundation, Bucharest